

ICCAR 2023 PROGRAM

Session 1.1			17 MAY 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-1	09:00-09:10	A Super-twisting SMC Design for Bidirectional DC–DC Converters in Electric Vehicle Applications	Ghadbane Houssam Eddine, Zorig Anwar and Dehmeche Ibrahim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 29
Y-2	09:10-09:20	Statistical mix design method for self-compacting concrete with limestone fillers	Brahim Nécira, Samir Djireb and Mounia Belkacem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 43
Y-3	09:20-09:30	Lemon Peel Extract as a Green Reducing Agent for Copper-Doped Titanium Nanotubes Synthesis	Meriem Gouasmi, Bilal Chikhi and Amel Boudjemaa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 59
Y-4	09:30-09:40	Numerical Modeling of Turbulent Biogas Combustion	Abdelkder Mahammedi, Naas Toufik Tayeb, D. Medjahed and Telha Mostefa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 62
Y-5	09:40-09:50	Enhancing Heart Disease Prediction using Deep Learning Model	Safa Gasmi, Akila Djebbar and Hayet Farida Merouani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 63
Y-6	09:50-10:00	On the enhancement of dc/dc converters dynamics using Gorilla Troop Optimizer based controller design.	BAKRIA Derradji, GOZIM Djamal, KORICH Belkacem and ELBAR Mohamed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 68
Y-7	10:00-10:10	An Enhanced Visual Object Tracking Approach using dual tree complex wavelet transform and Hierarchical Convolutional Features	Mohammed BOURENNANE and ELBAR Mohamed	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 69
Y-8	10:10-10:20	Control of Three-level Four Wire Shunt Active Power Filter in Grid-Connected PV-Fuel Cell System Employing Model Predictive Current Control Strategy	ELBAR Mohamed, KORICH Belkacem, BELADEL Abdelkader, DOURARI Ahmed Lamine, BAKRIA Derradji and TETA Ali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 70
Y-9	10:20-10:30	Maximum Power Point Tracking for Photovoltaic System under Partial Shading Conditions using Aquila Optimizer Algorithm	KORICH Belkacem, ELBAR Mohamed, BAKRIA Derradji, BELADEL Abdelkader, TETA Ali and DOURARI Ahmed Lamine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 71
Y-10	10:30-10:40	Study of Strong Electromagnetic-thermal Coupling Behavior in Induction Motor	REGAZ Amar, ELBAR Mohamed and DOURARI Ahmed Lamine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 72

Session 1.2			17 MAY 2023 09:00 11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-11	09:00-09:10	Reinforcement of concrete with composite materials based on fiberglass	Ahmed Lamine BENZERGA, Mohamed AMIEUR and Rachid RABEHI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 96
Y-12	09:10-09:20	Improving Random Forest with Pre-pruning technique for Binary classification	IlhemTarchoune, Akila Djebbar and Hayet Farida Merouani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 116
Y-13	09:20-09:30	Effectiveness of Mental and Physical Training on Blood Pressure and Resting Heart rate among Prehypertensive Young Adults	Imtiyaz Ali Mir, Anil T John, Mohammed Abdulrazzaq Jabbar, Syeda Humayra, Wan Cai Hui, Toh Xue Ying and Tan Jen Min	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 119
Y-14	09:30-09:40	Gas-hydrodynamics of gas-liquid flow in the reservoir-well system	Gunel Alizada	Azerbaijan	Submission 132
Y-15	09:40-09:50	Electrochemical and Mechanical Studies of Metal Parts Manufactured by CMT	BELLAL Youcef , BOUHANK Antar and ABABSA Abdelmadjid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 160
Y-16	09:50-10:00	Entropy generation of heat and mass transfer of humid-air inside an open cavity	Chati Tounsi, Naas Toufik Tayeb and Rouibah Abdelkader, Rahmani Kouider	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 166
Y-17	10:00-10:10	Evolution of Entropy Generation on Mixing Process Using a Novel Chaotic Micromixer	Naas Toufik Tayeb, Mahammedi Abdelkader and Chati Tounsi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 167
Y-18	10:10-10:20	Performance Enhancement of Wind Turbine System: Numerical Investigation	Naas Toufik Tayeb, Telha Mostefa and Chati Tounsi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 169
Y-19	10:20-10:30	Numerical Simulation of Unsteady Turbulent Flow and Heat Transfer of Dynamic Thermal Flow Sensor	Rouibah Abdelkader, Chati Tounsi and El bar Mohamed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 170
Y-20	10:30-10:40	The importance of databases in web programming	Najdovski Blagojche, Gordana Dimitrovska and Elena Joshevska	North Macedonia, North Macedonia, North Macedonia	Submission 180

Session 1.3			17 MAY 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-21	10:00-10:10	Fully Developed Laminar Flow of Heat Transfer Non-Newtonian Flow in Ducts with Arbitrary Cross-Sectional Shape	Naas Toufik Tayeb and Chati Tounsi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 200
Y-22	10:10-10:20	Heat transfer behaviour of mixing nano-non-Newtonian fluid in a chaotic micromixer	Naas Toufik Tayeb, Shakhawat Hossain and Chati Tounsi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 244
Y-23	10:20-10:30	Numerical investigation of Catalytic Combustion of Methane Using Wall Surface Reactions	Abdelkder Mahammedi, Naas Toufik Tayeb, A.Amari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 238
Y-24	10:30-10:40	Design and Management of a Photovoltaic Pumping System	Layate Zakaria, Bahi Tahar	Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 3
Y-25	10:40-10:50	Evaluation of hybridization between Apis mellifera subspecies in Albania	Manjola Kuliçi, Lejla Bejleri, Arbenita Hasani	Albania, Albania, Kosovo	Submission 156
Y-26	10:50-11:00	Is the consumption time of honey important to preserve its quality?	Manjola Kuliçi, Arbenita Hasani	Albania, Kosovo	Submission 157
Y-27	11:00-11:10	Framing Analysis of ChatGPT in Malaysian English Newspaper	Michelle Wong	Malaysia	Submission 184
Y-28	11:10-11:20	An Improved Multi-Pulse Rectifier Circuit for Input Current Harmonic Suppression Using Passive Devices	Abdul Wahab, Muhammad Ahmad Khurshid and Tahir Mahmood	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 205
Y-29	11:20-11:30	Impact of crushed sand replacement on the properties of sand concrete	Oday Jaradat, Karima Gadri and Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1
Y-30	11:30-11:40	Combination of Augmented Lagrangian and Uzawa Algorithm for Fluid-Structure Interaction Model	Ahmed Ayoub Boukelia, Nesrine Lamy Merabti and Abdelali Malek, Raouf Ziadi, Rim Benzatat, Ibtissam Daira, Nada Bentallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2

Session 1.4			17 MAY 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-31	10:00-10:10	Finite Volume Approach for the Incompressible Navier-Stokes Equations	Ahmed Ayoub Boukelia, Nesrine Lamya Merabti and Abdelali Malek, Raouf Ziadi, Rim Benzatat, Ibtissam Daira, Nada Bentallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3
Y-32	10:10-10:20	Solvability of a Parabolic-Hyperbolic Transmission Problem	Ahmed Ayoub Boukelia, Nesrine Lamya Merabti and Abdelali Malek, Raouf Ziadi, Rim Benzatat, Ibtissam Daira, Nada Bentallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4
Y-33	10:20-10:30	Finite Volume Method with penalty for Stokes Problem in 2 dimensions	Ahmed Ayoub Boukelia, Nesrine Lamya Merabti and Abdelali Malek, Raouf Ziadi, Rim Benzatat, Ibtissam Daira, Nada Bentallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5
Y-34	10:30-10:40	Informatics in business and its importance in business	Besnik Hajdari	Kosovo	Submission 7
Y-35	10:40-10:50	Auditing and its importance in the financial control of enterprises	Besnik Hajdari	Kosovo	Submission 8
Y-36	10:50-11:00	Analysis of flow problem without gravity effect	Benzatat Rim, F.Guechi and Hamid Benseridi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9
Y-37	11:00-11:10	Well-Posedness and Exponential Stability of Swelling Porous with Gurtin–Pipkin Thermoelasticity with distributed delay	Widad Karek, Lamine Bouzettouta and Abdallah Lallouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 10
Y-38	11:10-11:20	The Effect of The surface on Bidimensional Freeflow	Benzatat Rim, F.Guechi and Hamid Benseridi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 11
Y-39	11:20-11:30	An Amended Salp Swarm Optimization Algorithm using Chaos Theory	Nacer Meriem, Hamaizia Tayeb and Chabekh Meriem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 12
Y-40	11:30-11:40	Seed respiration during salt stress	Basti Asadova	Azerbaijan	Submission 13

Session 1.5			17 MAY 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-41	11:00-11:10	Salt expression as a defense mechanism during stress	Basti Asadova	Azerbaijan	Submission 14
Y-42	11:11-11:20	NUMERICAL STUDY FOR FRACTIONAL BI-MODAL 2019-nCOV Sitr EPIDEMIC MODEL	Benali Abdelkader	Algeria	Submission 15
Y-43	11:20-11:30	Initial Value Problem for Hybrid Generalized Hilfer Fractional Differential Equations	Benali Abdelkader	Algeria	Submission 16
Y-44	11:30-11:40	Method To Seek Traveling Wave Solutions For Some Fractional Nonlinear Pdes Arising In Natural Sciences	Benali Abdelkader	Algeria	Submission 17
Y-45	11:40-11:50	WELL-POSEDNESS AND GENERAL DECAY OF SOLUTIONS FOR A PETROVSKY EQUATION WITH A MEMORY TERM	Benali Abdelkader	Algeria	Submission 18
Y-46	11:50-12:00	Study The Asymptotic Behavior Of An Incompressible Herschel-Bulkley fluid	Abdelali Malek, Raouf ziadi, Abdelkader Saadallah, Ahmed Ayoub Boukelia, ibtissem दौरا, issra nada benatallah, Rim Benzatat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 19
Y-47	12:00-12:10	On the Asymptotic Behavior of an Interface Problem in a Thin Domain with Tresca boundary conditions	Abdelali Malek, Raouf ziadi, Abdelkader Saadallah, Ahmed Ayoub Boukelia, ibtissem दौरا, issra nada benatallah, Rim Benzatat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 20
Y-48	12:10-12:20	Asymptotic Behavior Of A Coupled System Of An Non-Newtonian Fluid And The Equation Of The Heat Energy	Abdelali Malek, Raouf ziadi, Abdelkader Saadallah, Ahmed Ayoub Boukelia, ibtissem दौरا, issra nada benatallah, Rim Benzatat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 21
Y-49	12:20-12:30	Study of a dynamical problem related to linear elasticity with nonlinear friction	Abdelali Malek, Raouf ziadi, Abdelkader Saadallah, Ahmed Ayoub Boukelia, ibtissem दौरا, issra nada benatallah, Rim Benzatat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 22
Y-50	12:30-12:40	A conjugate gradient algorithm for Global optimization via stochastic perturbation	Raouf Ziadi, Malek Abdelali, Ayoub Boukelia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 23

Session 1.6			17 MAY 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-51	11:00-11:10	RTQN: A mixed algorithm for smooth global optimization	Raouf Ziadi, Malek Abdelali, Ayoub Boukelia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 24
Y-52	11:11-11:20	AELS: Continuous global optimization through the generation of parametric curves	Raouf Ziadi, Malek Abdelali, Ayoub Boukelia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 25
Y-53	11:20-11:30	A stochastic conjugate gradient method for Global optimization	Raouf Ziadi, Malek Abdelali, Ayoub Boukelia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 26
Y-54	11:30-11:40	Refined plate theory for static bending behavior of FG plates	Farouk Yahia ADDOU, Fouad BOURADA, Imene AIT SIDHOUM, Mustapha MERADJAH, Mohamed BOURADA, Abdelouahed TOUNSI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 27
Y-55	11:40-11:50	Water treatment technologies in mining	Hadjer MEZAACHE, Yahia HAMMAR, Wahida KHERFANE and ALRIFAI Hazem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 30
Y-56	11:50-12:00	An overview of modern aeration techniques in aquatic systems	Hadjer MEZAACHE, Yahia HAMMAR, Wahida KHERFANE and ALRIFAI Hazem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 31
Y-57	12:00-12:10	Evaluation of methods for calculating dissolved oxygen in water: a comparative between direct dissolved oxygen method and Winkler method	Hadjer MEZAACHE, Yahia HAMMAR, Wahida KHERFANE, Abdelkader FIDJAH and Abdessattar AMMARI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 32
Y-58	12:10-12:20	Simulation and Analysis of high saline water membrane desalination	Sakhi Tayeb, Fidjah Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 33
Y-59	12:20-12:30	Literary translation and its stylistic analysis	Naim Kryeziu	Kosovo	Submission 35
Y-60	12:30-12:40	Prevalence of Anisakis spp. in Atlantic mackerel (<i>Scomber scombrus</i>) from Vlora Bay	Egon Andoni, Ani Vodica, Majlind Sulce, Pellumb Zalla, Enkeleda Ozuni	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 51

Session 1.7			17 MAY 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-61	12:00-12:10	Technical efficiency analysis of public research universities using Fuzzy Data Envelopment Analysis with ranking indicators as output variables	S.A.M. Ahmed, M.A. Talib, N.F.M. Noor and R. Jani	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 90
Y-62	12:11-12:20	Management of Public Finances in Kosovo according to legislation	Dafina Vlahna	Kosovo	Submission 136
Y-63	12:20-12:30	The importance of law enforcement for private international law	Argona Kuçi	USA	Submission 137
Y-64	12:30-12:40	The right of ownership as a real right based on legislation	Kastriote Vlahna	Kosovo	Submission 138
Y-65	12:40-12:50	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNIQUES IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF SERVICES PROVIDED BY E-GOVERNMENT TO CITIZENS	Mohammad Ali AL-Qudah, Leyla Muradkhanli	Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan	Submission 173
Y-66	12:50-13:00	Chatbots in Education: The impact of Artificial Intelligence based ChatGPT on Teachers and Students	Norbert Annuš	Slovakia	Submission 218
Y-67	13:00-13:10	Short-Term Electricity Price Forecasting Using EEMD and GRU-NN	Khalid Rashid Chughatta, Shaikh Saaqib Haroon	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 275
Y-68	13:10-13:20	Impact of the Size of Data on the Reliability of Short-Term Load Forecasting Using LSTM and GRU	Abdullah Ashraf and Shaikh Saaqib Haroon	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 276
Y-69	13:20-13:30	Improvement of the power quality by an active power filter controlled by backstepping	Nora Daou, Yacine Djeghader and Semma alami	Morocco, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 287
Y-70	13:30-13:40	Short-Term Load Forecasting Based on Bayesian Ridge Regression Coupled with an Optimal Feature Selection Technique	Abdullah Ashraf and Shaikh Saaqib Haroon	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 290

Session 1.8			17 MAY 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-71	12:00-12:10	Smart Agricultural System Using AI	Jamilu Sulaiman, Majeed Hussain Mohammed Abdul	Nigeria, France	Submission 300
Y-72	12:11-12:20	Environmental Sanitation Monitoring System Using Drone and Artificial Intelligence	Jamilu Sulaiman, Majeed Hussain Mohammed Abdul	Nigeria, France	Submission 302
Y-73	12:20-12:30	Applications of the statistical convergence and of the ideals in integration	Anita Caushi	Kosovo	Submission 312
Y-74	12:30-12:40	The image processing for creating 3D model in teaching computer science	Krisztina Czakóová	Slovakia	Submission 308
Y-75	12:40-12:50	LINGUISTIC PROBLEMS IN THE TERMINOLOGICAL LEXICION OF INFORMATICS IN THE ALBANIAN LANGUAGE	ESMERALDA STRORI	Albania	Submission 229
Y-76	12:50-13:00	Modeling and Simulation of a cooking inductors by Electromagnetic Induction	Fatima Zohra Aroua, Ahmed Salhi, Rezig Mohamed and Djemai Naimi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 216
Y-77	13:00-13:10	Analysis of the buckling of magneto-piezoelectric nano-plates by the theory of nonlocal elasticity	M. Messaoud, M. Bouazza	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 278
Y-78	13:10-13:20	Random number-based Brownian motion and practical examples of its implementing in high school computer science lessons	Dávid Paksi, Norbert Annuš, Iveta Štempeľová and Daniel Dancsa	Slovakia, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Slovakia	Submission 322
Y-79	13:20-13:30	Development of Intelligent Shopping Cart using Pixy Sensor with Arduino Controller	Danish Nouman, M. Bilal Khalid Keyani, Mian Farhan Ullah and M. Idrees Hassan Raza	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 143
Y-80	13:30-13:40	An Overview of Downhole Electrical Machines and their Benefits	Danish Nouman, Mian Farhan Ullah, Syed Hammd Haider, M. Bilal Khalid Keyani	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 303

Session 1.9			17 MAY 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-81	12:00-12:10	Assessment of Genetic variability among ethidium bromide-derived genotypes of cowpea (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> (L.) Walp) at M7 generation	A. T Ajayi, O. S Osekita, T. F. Ojo, O. E. Omoniyi	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 234
Y-82	12:11-12:20	In-silico study of allergenic proteins of certain food legumes: peanut, lentil, sesame and cowpea	Hamidani Lydia, Arioua Khalil, Zeyneb Djeflal, Boutebba Aissa	Algeria, Russia, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 199
Y-83	12:20-12:30	THEMES OF GRAMMATICAL FORMS IN THE NOMINATIVE SYSTEM	Gilberta Hadaj, Albana Tahiri	Albania, Albania	Submission 304
Y-84	12:30-12:40	Developing a Low-Cost IoT based Remote Cardiovascular Patient Monitoring System in Pakistan	Muhammad Awais, Reqad Ali, Jawaid Iqbal, Fahim Shahzad	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 239
Y-85	12:40-12:50	Improved Control Method for Voltage Regulation and Harmonic Mitigation Using Dynamic Voltage Restorer	Anees Ullah, Gull Rukh, Jalil Ahmad and Mian Farhan Ullah	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 262
Y-86	12:50-13:00				
Y-87	13:00-13:10				
Y-88	13:10-13:20				
Y-89	13:20-13:30				
Y-90	13:30-13:40				

Session 2.5			18 MAY 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-17	13:00-13:10	STUDY SOME MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 2024-AL ALLOY REINFORCED BY MICRO AND NANO CERAMIC PARTICLES	Mhmood Salim Hassoon, İsmail Hakkı KARA, Ahmed H. Ali, Abdullah YILDIZ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 1
T-18	13:10-13:20	Trend analysis and drought evaluation: A case study of Sırnak	Veysi KARTAL	Turkey	Submission 6
T-19	13:20-13:30	Neural Network and Random Forest Algorithms for Estimation of the Waiting Times Based on the DES in ED	Abdulkadir Atalan	Turkey	Submission 37
T-20	13:30-13:40	The PhotoVoice method in Science, Social, and Environmental Education	Mustafa Derman	Turkey	Submission 47
T-21	13:40-13:50	Artificial Intelligence and Sustainability	Pınar Cihan	Turkey	Submission 50
T-22	13:50-14:00	Improving Raisin Grains Classification with a Hybrid PSO-NN Approach	Mahmut Dirik	Turkey	Submission 80
T-23	14:00-14:10	Experimental Investigation of Centrifugal Pump Characteristics	İsmet Sezer, Yiğit Serkan Şahin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 95
T-24	14:10-14:20	Makine Öğrenmesi Algoritması ile Çanakkale İlinin Güneş Işınım Şiddetinin Analizi	Necla TEKTAŞ, Ebru KORKMAZ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 103
T-25	14:20-14:30	Biofabrication: Lab-Grown Animal Products	Meruyert KAYGUSUZ	Turkey	Submission 107
T-26	14:30-14:40	Bir Kaynak Operatörünün Çalışma Maruziyetinin QEC Tekniği ile Değerlendirilmesi	Bekir GÜNEY, Mehmet Akif ERDEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 109

Session 2.6			18 MAY 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-27	13:00-13:10	Ankara İçin Engelsiz Toplu Ulaşım Mobil Uygulaması Projesi	Merve ÜN, Necla TEKTAŞ, Mehmet TEKTAŞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 110
T-28	13:10-13:20	Applications Of Algae as a Functional Food Additive in Meat Products	Emel Kaynakçı	Turkey	Submission 113
T-29	13:20-13:30	Antioxidant and Antibacterial Activity Properties of Polymeric Ligand-Metal Complexes	Aysel AYDIN KOCAEREN	Turkey	Submission 120
T-30	13:30-13:40	Power inequalities for the Berezin radius of operators in functional Hilbert spaces	Mehmet Gürdal and Orçun Yücel	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 147
T-31	13:40-13:50	THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION APPREHENSION AND PROFESSIONAL LEARNING LEVEL AMONG FOREIGN NATIONAL MIDWIFERY STUDENTS	Ayşe Çuvadar, Suzan Onur	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 151
T-32	13:50-14:00	Experimental investigation of the effects of 7% ethanol and 7% isopropanol added to standard diesel fuel on engine vibration and noise	Nurullah Gültekin, Halil Erdi Gülcan and Murat Ciniviz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 159
T-33	14:00-14:10	Kırmızı Lahananın Toplam Fenolik Madde ve Antioksidan Aktivitesi Üzerinde pH ve Ekstraksiyon Süresinin Etkisi	Aye SEYHAHMET, Zuhale SAHİN, Fatih SONMEZ, Mustafa KUCUKISLAMOĞLU	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 178
T-34	14:10-14:20	Ekstraksiyon Süresinin ve pH Değerinin Kırmızı Pancarda Toplam Fenolik Madde ve Antioksidan Aktivitesi Üzerinde Etkisinin İncelenmesi	Rama ALKAYARI, Zuhale SAHİN, Fatih SONMEZ, Mustafa KUCUKISLAMOĞLU	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 179
T-35	14:20-14:30	ZnS İnce Filmlerinin Termiyonik Vakum Ark (TVA) Tekniği İle Elde Edilmesi ve Optik ve Yüzey Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Saliha Elmas	Turkey	Submission 181
T-36	14:30-14:40	A Comparison Of Ottoman And Western Coffehouses/Cafes In Terms Of Political Functionality On The Historical Background	Emre Yıldırım	Turkey	Submission 182

Session 2.7			18 MAY 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-37	14:00-14:10	Pirinç Nişastası Bazlı Film Üretimi Ve İlaç Salınımında Kullanımının Araştırılması	Merve Ögünç, Evren Arıöz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 188
T-38	14:10-14:20	Gayrimenkul Değerlemede Yapay Sinir Ağlarının Kullanılması	Cengiz SERTKAYA, Zekeriya KÖSE	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 192
T-39	14:20-14:30	Circularly Polarized L-Shaped Defected Ground Antenna for WLAN Communication Systems	Aynur Sena Çetinkaya, Merih Palandöken	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 195
T-40	14:30-14:40	Bütünleşik Pazarlama İletişiminde CRM Yazılımı Kullanımının Önemi	Mehmet Ekim AYYILDIZ, Aşkın Nurdan TÜMBEK TEKEOĞLU	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 198
T-41	14:40-14:50	The Mediating Role of Emotion Regulation in the Relationship between Self-Compassion and Subjective Well-Being in School in Secondary School Students	Lokman KOÇAK, Elif TERZİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 202
T-42	14:50-15:00	Conjugated Polymers for Photo-electrochromic Devices	Buket Bezgin Carbas	Turkey	Submission 208
T-43	15:00-15:10	Electrochromic Glass Design with Solar Energy	Buket Bezgin Carbas, Senem Düzgün	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 209
T-44	15:10-15:20	Production and Performance of Dye Sensitive Solar Cells Using Co+2 Doped Photo-Anodes	Berrak Çalışkan, Enes Şayan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 213
T-45	15:20-15:30	Otomotiv Endüstrisinde Döngüsel Ekonomi ve Elektrikli Araçlar İçin Yaşam Döngüsü Değerlendirmesinin İncelenmesi	Sermin GÜNASLAN, Berrak EROL NALBUR, S.Sıddık CİNDORUK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 215
T-46	15:30-15:40	The importance of classification in reducing the congestion price in peer-to-peer energy trading	Amir Hanari, Mustafa Baysal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 228

Session 2.8			18 MAY 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-47	14:00-14:10	Using the Power of Instagram: Instagram as a Suitable Channel for Making Advocacy Campaigns to Decrease Violence Against Women	Randa Jamal ALDAWOUDI, Askım Nurdan Tümbek TEKEOGLU	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 2
T-48	14:10-14:20	ARAÇ SOĞUTMA SİSTEMLERİNDE KULLANILAN HIZLI BAĞLANTI ELEMANLARINDA FORM YAPISININ TAKMA KUVVETİNE ETKİSİNİN ANALİZİ	Hikmet ULAŞ, Ömer ALGÜL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 189
T-49	14:20-14:30	E-Ticarette Tüketici Güvenliği ve Veri Gizliliği Sağlamada Blockchain Teknolojilerinin Kullanımı	Hamza ÇAKMAK, Murat Fatih TUNA	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 197
T-50	14:30-14:40	THINK EAT SAVE HAREKETİ SOSYAL AFİŞİNİN GÖSTERGEBİLİMSSEL AÇIDAN İNCELENMESİ	Merve Ersan, Oğuzhan Aras	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 206
T-51	14:40-14:50	Li-iyon Piller için Kalay Oksit Esaslı Kompozit Anot Malzemeler ve Yenilikçi Yaklaşımlar	Miraç Alaf	Turkey	Submission 214
T-52	14:50-15:00	GRAFİK TASARIM SEKTÖRÜNDE YAPAY ZEKANIN KULLANILMASI (MİDJOURNEY)	Birsen Çeken, Oğuzhan Şen	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 217
T-53	15:00-15:10	Reklamlarda Cinsiyet Temsili: “Yazar Kulaklıkları” Reklam Kampanyasının Göstergebilimsel Yöntemle İncelenmesi	Merve Ersan, Ozan Emen	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 231
T-54	15:10-15:20	EXPLORING THE LANDSCAPE OF SDN-BASED DDOS DEFENSE: A HOLISTIC EXAMINATION OF DETECTION AND MITIGATION APPROACHES, RESEARCH GAPS AND PROMISING AVENUES FOR FUTURE EXPLORATION	Tasnim ALASALI and Omar DAKKAK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 243
T-55	15:20-15:30	Fourier tabanlı Senkrosıkıştırma Dönüşümü Kullanarak LSTM ile Solunum Seslerinin Sınıflandırılması	Yücel KOÇYİĞİT	Turkey	Submission 271
T-56	15:30-15:40	FDM YÖNTEMİ KULLANILARAK FARKLI ÜRETİM PARAMETRELERİNE GÖRE ÜRETİLEN PLA+ BAZLI ÇEKME NUMUNELERİNİN ÇEKME YÖNÜNDEKİ DAVRANIŞLARININ DENEYSEL OLARAK İNCELENMESİ	Kürşat Kurtoğlu, Gökşan ŞAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 273

Session 2.9			18 MAY 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-57	15:00-15:10	Deep Learning Architectures Performance in Plant Leaf Diseases	Yunus Emre Karaca, Serpil Aslan, Muhammed Yıldırım	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 274
T-58	15:10-15:20	Conducting polymer effects on hybrid S-rGO/CuO/polymer nanocomposites for SupercapBattery devices	Murat Ates	Turkey	Submission 279
T-59	15:20-15:30	Sulfur dopant effects on hybrid rGO/MoS2/PANI nanocomposites for SupercapBattery devices	Murat Ates	Turkey	Submission 280
T-60	15:30-15:40	SENTIMENT ANALYSIS BASED ON MACHINE LEARNING METHODS ON TWITTER DATA USING oneAPI	Fatih Şengül, Kemal Adem and Esra Kavalcı Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 282
T-61	15:40-15:50	Game Theoretical Perspectives on Cooperation and Competition in Banking Sector	Fatmanur Oral, Meryem Aysin and Gürkan Çalmaşur	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 299
T-62	15:50-16:00	Risk Analysis and Risk Assessment of Laboratory Work by Fine Kinney Method	Vedat Karahan and Ercan Aydoğmuş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 306
T-63	16:00-16:10	Effects of Dispersion Medium on Surface Tension and Rheological Behavior of Pectin and Guar Gum Based Thickeners Used in Treatment of Dysphagia	Mukaddes Karataş and Ercan Aydoğmuş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 310
T-64	16:10-16:20	The Impact of Blockchain Technology on E-commerce Supply Chain Management	Abdullah Önden	Turkey	Submission 267
T-65	16:20-16:30	Decision making towards improvement of service provision through data derived from Quality Control Performance Measurement: the case of Izmir Bakircay University Institute	Ourania Areta Hızıroğlu, Doğa Tümerdem	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 112
T-66	16:30-16:40	YSZ Termal Bariyer Kaplamanın Elektroforetik Nano-YSZ Kaplama ile Korozyon Direncinin İyileştirilmesi	Abdulkadir ÖZÇELİK, Ali AVCI, Muhammet KARABAŞ, Ayşegül AKDOĞAN EKER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 219

Session 2.10			18 MAY 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-67	15:00-15:10	Moda Perspektifinde Boş Zaman ve Çalışma Hayatı	Muazzez Çetiner	Turkey	Submission 232
T-68	15:10-15:20	Oyun İçerikli Reklamların Gıda Sektöründe Kullanılabilirliği ve Örnekleri	Birsen Çeken, Ozan Emen	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 277
T-69	15:20-15:30	A Novel Metamaterial-Based Dual-Band Polarization Insensitive Wide Angle Absorber for Refractive Index Sensing	Serhane Abdelkader, Berka Mohammed, Umut Özkaya, Bendaoudi Amina and Mahdjoub Zoubir	Algeria, Algeria, Turkey, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 285
T-70	15:30-15:40	Üniversitelerde Kurulan Dijital Dönüşüm Ofislerinin İncelenmesi: Türkiye Örneği	Başak EPLİ, Asım Oğuzhan ALTUNKAYA, M. Hanefi CALP	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 286
T-71	15:40-15:50	The Effects of Common Macroeconomics Factors on U.S. Stock Returns	Serkan Sengul	Turkey	Submission 292
T-72	15:50-16:00	Low-Profile Elliptic Complementary Metamaterial Resonator-Based UWB Antenna for Wireless Communications	Berka Mohammed, Umut Özkaya, Sudipta Das, Baghdad Bey Abdelkader, Bendaoudi Amina, Serhane Abdelkader and Mahdjoub Zoubir	Algeria, Turkey, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria,	Submission 297
T-73	16:00-16:10	PID control of a zero stiffness magnetic suspension system	Ergin Kılıç, Berkan Kuşcu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 305
T-74	16:10-16:20	COMPARISON OF RISK ANALYSIS METHODS WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY	Muhammet Fatih AK, Müge Begüm ARSLAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 318
T-75	16:20-16:30	Mobile Phone Price Classification Using Machine Learning	Seda İpek AKSOY ERCAN, Murat ŞİMŞEK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 319
T-76	16:30-16:40	Investigation of the Effect of V Particles Added to Steels Manufactured by Powder Metallurgy	Mehmet Akif Erden, Mehmet Akkaş	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 4

Session 2.11			18 MAY 2023 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-150	16:00-16:10	Investigation of Manufacturability of WC Particle Reinforced Steels by Powder Metallurgy Method	Hasan Gökçe	Turkey	Mail Submission 5
T-151	16:10-16:20	An examination of parkinson's speech data with multilayer perceptron	Ramiz Görkem Birdal	Turkey	Submission 284
T-152	16:20-16:30				
T-153	16:30-16:40				
T-154	16:40-16:50				
T-155	16:50-17:00				
T-156	17:00-17:10				
T-157	17:10-17:20				
T-158	17:20-17:30				
T-159	17:30-17:40				